

Link Between Classical Spatial Density for Constant Speed, Momentum and Quantum Mechanics

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We have tried to link $\exp(ipx)$, the quantum free particle wavefunction, to the classical spatial density $P(x)=1/L$ as well as to conservation of momentum in previous notes. Here, we try to present an argument which follows from two ideas: conservation of momentum and $P_1(p_1+p_2,x)=P_1(p_3+p_4,x)$ for $p_1+p_2=p_3+p_4$. These ideas seem to be consistent with classical physics, but lead to the quantum result $\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}$.

Classical Probability Density and Conservation of Momentum

It is well known that a classical particle with a constant speed spends the same amount of time dt in each fixed dx and so one may write a classical spatial probability density:

$$P(x) dx = dx/L \quad ((1))$$

It is also known classically that conservation of momentum exists. In such a case, one has:

$$P_1 + p_2 = p_3+p_4 \text{ (vectors)} \quad ((2)) \text{ with a collision occurring at } x_t$$

If $P(x)$ shows a particle's probability in space, given that impulses are physical and proportional to momentum, we argue that one is justified in insisting on the existence of:

$$P_1(p,x) \quad ((3))$$

At first one would consider:

$$P_1(p,x) = P(x) \quad ((4))$$

In other words, momentum as well as the particle identity resides at the center-of-mass point.

The problem is that if one takes an unnormalized $P_1(p,x)$ and writes an AND scenario:

$$P_1(p_1,x)(\text{unnormalized}) P_1(p_2,x) \text{ unnormalized} = P_1(p_1+p_2, x) \text{ unnormalized} \quad ((5))$$

((5)) is directly linked to the idea of conservation of momentum in a loose sense and shows that one has an issue with classical thinking. To see this more clearly, consider a particle with p and a particle with $-p$. If one is only interested in the probability of having momentum (not a single particle) at x , then:

$$P_1(p,x) \text{ unnormalized} P_1(-p,x) \text{ unnormalized} = P_1(0, x) \quad ((6))$$

$P_1(p,x)$ is a scheme which does not keep track of particle density necessarily, but is focused on momentum density/probability. If one uses $P_1(p,x)=P(x)$, then the probability to have 0 momentum is the same as $P_1(p,x)$, the probability of having momentum. One would rather have:

$$P_1(p_1+p_2,x)_{\text{unnormalized}} = P_1(p_3+p_4,x)_{\text{unnormalized}} \text{ if } p_1+p_2=p_3+p_4 \quad ((6b))$$

(An analogue of ((6b)) appears in classical statistical mechanics in the case of the Maxwell-Boltzmann gas for which: $p(e_1)p(e_2)=p(e_3)p(e_4)$ unnormalized if $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$. In that case, conservation of energy is the key.

((6b)) is a probabilistic description of net momentum which does not distinguish between which momenta create the same net result. In other words, as stated, the focus is simply on the net momentum present which describes the kind of interaction which occurs.

Next consider:

$$P_1(0,x)_{\text{unnormalized}} * P_1(p_2,x) = P_1(p_2,x) \quad ((7))$$

Here there are now three particles, but one is only interested in overall momentum (because this pertains to impulse hits). ((7)) implies that:

$$P_1(p,x) = \text{constant power } (i p f(x)) \quad ((8))$$

There is no reason for $P_1(p,x)$ to favour one x point versus another so it seems that one is forced to adopt:

$$P_1(p,x) = \text{constant power } (i p x) \quad ((9))$$

((9)) is derived to describe momentum in space, not particles in space. ((9)) may be the product of various $\exp(ipx)$ values representing different particles because one wishes to have a probability describing the net momentum available which is applicable to an interaction.

The last step is to impose conservation of momentum. If one considers $P_1(p,x)P_1(-p,x)=1$ from ((9)), then:

$$P_1(-p_1,x) P_1(p_2,x)_{\text{unnormalized}} = \text{constant } (i (-p_1+p_2) x) \quad ((10))$$

If $-p_1+p_2 \neq 0$, then one should have a violation of conservation of momentum and the probability should be zero. Thus, one has a problem with enforcing classical $p_1+p_2= p_3+p_4$ (vectors) classical conservation of momentum in this scenario and that is a serious drawback. In particular, there is no reason to have a probability scheme for p in x if it does not ensure conservation of momentum.

There seems to be one way to enforce momentum conservation, but that means breaking with the notion of classical physics having infinite resolution in x , i.e. with an interaction occurring at a specific x point. If instead, one gives up infinite x resolution, then one may consider a small range about x and argue that momentum conservation occurs by considering this range, i.e. by adding probabilities ((10)) within this range. Thus one may propose:

$$\text{Constant} = \exp \quad ((11))$$

$$\text{In such a case: } \exp(ipx) = \cos(px) + i \sin(px) \quad ((11))$$

By introducing periodicity, one may achieve conservation of momentum, but at the cost of classical infinite resolution.

Actually, $\exp(ipx)$ needs to be adjusted so that px is dimensionless, i.e.

$$px/\text{constant} \text{ should be used. } \quad ((12))$$

From the theory of a photon, one knows that: $p = \hbar k$ ((13)).

Then, one has a theory which applies equally well to photons and massive particles and is based on momentum conservation linked with a probability in space (albeit a complex one) which does not allow for infinite x resolution and so enforces momentum conservation within a wavelength of $\exp(i(p_1+p_2)x)$.

Interaction Versus Center-of-Mass Motion

The key basis of the above argument is that if the classical probability $P(x)dx$ exists, and it seems to, then one is justified in arguing that there should be a probability for momentum in space (as this is related to interactions). We argue that $P(x)$ is linked to the position of the particle, i.e. its center of mass. Normally, momentum would be considered to be taken at the same center-of-mass point, but the above arguments argue that it cannot, essentially due to the constraint of conservation of momentum which forces one to adopt \exp as the constant in ((10)). Together with i in the power, leading to a periodic scenario for interactions with momentum.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that if one defines $P(x)dx$ in classical physics for a particle with constant v , then one is justified in defining $P_1(p,x)$ to describe momentum in space. At first one would expect $P_1(p,x) = P(x) = 1/L$ (L is an arbitrary length) as the momentum classically is taken at the center-of-mass of the particle, just like the particle's identity. The problem is that this does not allow for a description of multiple particles which have momentum and may be at the same x point. One then has: $P_1(p_1,x) \text{ unnormalized} * P_1(p_2,x) \text{ unnormalized} = P_1(p_1+p_2,x) \text{ unnormalized}$. In this case, one uses P_1 to describe net momentum and cannot use the constant $P(x)=1/L$. One is developing a probabilistic expression for momentum in space and $P_1(p_1+p_2,x)$ is not the same as $P_1(p_2+p_3,x)$, even in a classical scenario of particles moving with constant speed. Alternatively, one may consider $p_1=-p_2$. In such a case, $P_1(0, x)$, the

probability to have 0 momentum in space should not be the same as $P_1(p,x)$, i.e. the probability of having no momentum in space. In particular, one wants $P_1(p_1+p_2,x)=P_1(p_3+p_4,x)$ if $p_1+p_2=p_3+p_4$. This leads to: $P_1(p,x) = \text{constant}$ (p f(x) i) because one cannot have $P_1(p,x)$ bias x space for constant speeds. In fact, $f(x)=x$ for the same reason. Finally, to obtain conservation of momentum, one is forced to give up the classical notion of infinite resolution in x and use constant $=e xp$ in order to obtain a periodic solution. Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ is based on two ideas, conservation of momentum and the notion that $P_1(p_1+p_2,x)=P_1(p_3+p_4,x)$ if $p_1+p_2=p_3+p_4$ and seems to be a way of describing net momenta in space in such a way that one does not distinguish between the constituent momenta when they combine and one ensures conservation of momentum.